

ROLE OF PATHYA IN RASACHIKITSA: A CRITICAL REVIEW**Dr. Aarzoo Panchal^{1*}, Prof. (Dr) Ravi Raj²**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Rasa Chikitsa utilizes potent herbo-mineral formulations that require careful regulation to ensure safety and therapeutic efficacy. Classical Rasashastra literature emphasizes the observance of Pathya-Apathya during Rasaushadhi administration due to their Tikshna and Sukshma properties. **Objective:** To critically review the role of Pathya in Rasa Chikitsa with reference to classical Rasashastra texts and its relevance in clinical practice. **Materials and Methods:** Classical Rasashastra texts and relevant Ayurvedic literature were reviewed to compile common and drug-specific Pathya-Apathya Ahara prescribed during Rasadravya administration. The collected data were analyzed and interpreted critically. **Results:** Pathya was found to play a significant role in supporting digestion, absorption, and assimilation of Rasaushadhis, thereby enhancing therapeutic efficacy and reducing adverse effects. Variations in dietary recommendations across different texts indicate the need for

individualized and context-based application. **Conclusion:** Pathya is an integral component of Rasa Chikitsa and directly influences the safety and effectiveness of Rasaushadhi therapy. Re-emphasizing dietary regulation in clinical practice is essential for the rational and safe application of Rasa Chikitsa in contemporary Ayurveda.

KEYWORDS: Rasa Chikitsa, Pathya, Rasaushadhi, Rasashastra, Pathya-Apathya.

INTRODUCTION

The term "Rasa" refers to the medications employed in the therapeutic use of Rasa shastra in Rasa chikitsa. The preparation and therapeutic use of mercurial, metallic, mineral, toxic plant, and some animal products are the focus of this area of Ayurveda.^[1] The processed metal and mineral formulation are given in various forms such as Shodhana, Bhavana, Marana and others. These medications are called Rasaushadhis.

In context of Ayurveda, "Pathya" refers to a regimen or dietary guidelines that are considered beneficial or conducive to health. By following to Pathya, individual aim to maintain or Restore health, aligning themselves with the natural rhythms and needs of their bodies.^[2]

पथ्यं पथोऽनपेतं यद्यच्चोक्तं मनसः प्रियम्। यच्चाप्रियमपथ्यं च नियतं तन्न लक्षयेत्^[3]॥
(Cha.Su. 25/45)

Pathya refers to dietary and lifestyle practices that are considered beneficial for health. These practices typically include Food, behaviours, and routines that help calm the mind, nourish the body and promote overall well being. Pathya emphasizes consuming wholesome, nutritious foods following regular routine and engaging in activities that supports mental and physical health.

On the other hand, Apathya refers to practices that are considered detrimental to health. These may include consuming unhealthy foods, following irregular or unhealthy routines, and engaging in behaviors that disrupt mental and physical well-being. Apathya is the opposite of Pathya and is generally avoided or minimized to maintain optimal health according to Ayurvedic Principles.^[4]

According to Vaidya Lolimbakra in his book "Vaidyajivnam" describe pathya as

“पथ्येऽसति गदार्त्तस्य किमौषधनिसेवणै। पथ्ये सति गदार्त्तस्य किमौषधानिसेवण”^{[11][5]}

It said that if patient is following the dietary rules there is no need of medicines because person hardly suffers from diseases and if patient is not following the dietary rules again there is also nix need of medicines because medicines may not be effective.

Pathya kalpana is intimately associated with diet and it's nutritional value. The cardinal parts of Ayurveda treatment are diet and medicine. Diet is dominated with taste and recognized by it's nutritional value whereas medicine is dominated with therapeutic potency (Virya) and recognized by it's therapeutic efficacy.

[वीर्य प्रधानमौषधाद्रव्यं, तथा रसप्रधानमाहारद्रव्यं [च.]^[6]

In contemporary knowledge diets are mainly classified as per their nutritional domain like carbohydrate, fats, proteins, minerals and vitamins. Where as in Ayurveda, diets are classified according to their taste and therapeutic utility in accordance with Panchabhautik composition and Tridosha theory. Depending on the constitutional nature (as per Pancha-mahabhuta and Tridosha theory) of the patient, required diet of appropriate nutritional and therapeutic value is advised. If Kapha is the cause of disease, then the diet having, opposite constitutional properties for Kapha i.e. diet dominating Tikta (bitter taste), Amla (sour taste) rasa are advised to take, for facilitating the quick therapeutic effect of medicines given. Pathya ahara (right dietary regimen) effectively control the therapeutic efficacy of the medicines; hence Acharya Kasyap has rightly called Ahara (diet) Maha-bheshaja (great medicine).

[न च आहार समं किञ्चिद् भैषज्यमुपलभ्यते... महाभैषज्यमुच्यते]^[7]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table 1. Pathya Ahara during Rasa Bhasma Sevana.^[8]

S.No.	Dravya	Guna	Karma
1.	Dugdha(Milk)	Madhura vipaka, sheet virya, snigdha guna	
2.	Shali anna (rice)	Madhura Kashaya rasa, Snigdha laghu guna, sheet virya	
3.	Mudga(Green Gram)	Madhura rasa, laghu guna	Kapha pitta nashaka and jwara nashaka
4.	Ghrita (ghee)	Madhur vipaka, sheet virya	Tridosahara, ojo vardhaka
5.	Punarnava, Meghnada, Vastukaa along with saindhava, Shunthi, Musta and Padmamoola	Madhura rasa, laghu gna	Anuloma, vatashamaka
6.	Godhuma (wheat preparations)	Madhura rasa, Guru guna, Sheet virya	Balakarka
7.	Dadhi(curd)	Kashaya rasa, amla vipaka	Pittakaphahara, bala vardhaka
8.	Hamsodaka(water)	Laghu guna	Triptikara
9.	Mudgayush(Green gram soup)	Madhura rasa, Laghu guna	
10.	Takram hitam snehagatam(butter milk without fat)	Laghu guna	
11.	Pushpa(flowers)		
12.	Sarva phala madhuram(sweet fruits)	Prithwi and jala mahabhoota predominance	

	Pakyukta mamsa sharkaram (properly prepared meat and sugar preparations		Balya, vata shamaka
13.	Purana shali (rice that has been kept)	Laghu guna	Balya, brumhaniya
14.	Sarva madhuram(sweet substances)	Prithwi and jala mahabhoot	Vata shamaka

Table 2: Apathya Ahara during Rasa Bhasma Sevana.^[9]

S.no.	Apathya Ahara	S.no.	Apathya Ahara
1.	Atyashana(over eating)	24	Bilva (Aegle marmelos)
2.	Atipana(excess drinking)	25	Kushmanda (pumpkin)
3	Adhamanahara(Food that cause bloating)	26	Vetagra(Bambusa arundinacea)
4	Kakarashtaka gana (chelating agents)	27	Karpoora(Camphor)
5	Kulattha (horse gram)	28	Karvellaka(Bitter gourd)
6	Atasi tailaa(linseed oil)	29	Nishpava(Vigna unguiculata)
7	Chitra taila	30	Sarshapa(mustard seed)
8	Tila (sesame oil)	31	Sahakara
9	Masha (black gram)	32	Surasava(Alcoholic preparations)
10	Masooraka(red lentils)	33	Anupa mamsa (meat of animals residing in wet lands)
11	Kapotha mamsa(meat of pigeon)	34	Dhanyamla(Sour liquids)
12	Kanjika (sour gruel)	35	Guru Vishtambhi ahara (heavy and dry foods)
13	Takranna (buttermilk rice(36	Teekshanoshana ahara (hopt and pungent food)
14	Kukutta mamsa(meat of hen)	37	Lavanadhikam (food mixed with more salt)
15	Lavana, amla, katu tikta ahara(salt sour pungent and bitter foods)	38	Sandhyajya annam (food that is kept overnight)
16	Pittala patra (usage of bronze vessels)	39	Keshadi Rustam (food contaminated by hair)
17	Badara (Jujube fruits)	40	Kritasheetha ushnam (reboiled food)
18	Narikela (coconut)	41	Shakhavarannai bhaulam (food with more leafy vegetables than rice)
19	Saindhava lavana (rock salt)	42	Atyambupana (drinking excessive liquids)
20	Sauvarchala lavana (black salt)	43	Svadu heenam (tasteless food)
21	Naranga (lemon)	44	Vinastha dugdha (spoiled milk)
22	Kanchnara (Bauhinia varigata)	45	Amahara (improperly cooked food)
23	Bruhati (Solanum indicum)	46	Dagdhahara (burnt food)

Table 3; Dietary regimen during Rasabhasma sevan.

S.no.	Dravya	Pathya	Apathya
1	Parada ^[10]	Mudaga, dugdhanna, shalianna, shakam (loki, patol, vastuk) Punarnava, meghnada, saindhava, nagara, musta, padamoola	Kushmand, karkati, kalingak, karvellaka, kusumbh, karkotaki, kadali, kakmachi
2.	Parada ^[11]	Ghrita saindhava jeerak aadrak dhanyak tanduliyak, patol, jeeran godhoom, shali annam, godugdh, goghrita, dadhi, Hansodaka, mudagra	Brihati, Bilva, Kushmanda, Vetrakra, Karvellaka, Masha, Mashoor, Nishvapa, Kulitha, Sarshapa, Tila, Langhana, Uadvartana, Sanna, Tamrachuda, Sura, Aasava, Aanoopamamsa, Dhanyamla, Kadli dala or kamsya bhojana, Guru, Vishtambhi, Tikshana, Ushna
3.	Abhrak ^[12]		Kshara, Amla, Divdala, Karkati, Karvellaka, Vrutaka, Karira, Taila
4.	Shilajit ^[13]	Mahrndra salila sevana, Kopa ambu, Dwiguna kala parivarjana	Vyayama, Aatapa, Maruta, Santapi, Atiguru, Vidahi anna
5.	Gandhaka ^[14]	Jangal mamsa, chaagal mamsa	Lavana, amla katu vidahi, patrashak, dwidala anna, kshara, kanji stri sevan, yana arohana
6.	Shilajit ^[15]	Satu, Saindhva, Madhura rasa sevana	Lavana-Amla Katu rasa, Vahni- Aatapa varjayeta
7.	Loha ^[16]		Kushmand, tilataila, masha anna, rajika, madya, amla, masoor
8.	Visha ^[17]	Ghrita, Kshira, Sita, Kshodra, Godhooma, Tandula, Maricha, Saindhva, Draksha, Madhura panaka, Hima, Brahmacharya, Hima deshs- Hima kala- Hima jala	Katu, Amla, Lavana, Tiala, Diwaswapna, Anala Aatapa sevana
9.	Suvarna ^[18]	Dugdha, Sarkara, Snigdha anna	Kakrashataka anna and Mamsa

than uniform dietary restrictions. In present-day practice, inadequate attention to Pathya often compromises therapeutic outcomes, reinforcing the need to re-emphasize its role in rational Rasa Chikitsa.

CONCLUSION

Pathya forms a foundational component of Rasa Chikitsa and directly influences the safety and effectiveness of Rasaushadhi therapy. Classical texts clearly demonstrate that both general and drug-specific dietary regimens are designed to support digestion, enhance drug action, and minimize toxicity. The findings of this review emphasize that Pathya should be individualized and integrated thoughtfully into clinical practice. Re-establishing the importance of Pathya is essential for the safe, effective, and rational application of Rasa Chikitsa in contemporary Ayurvedic therapeutics.

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